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coefficient and n the number of electrons involved in reduction, have been evaluated by the modified method of Oldham and Parry⁶. According to these authors, the equation for an irreversible diffusion-controlled wave is

$$-E_{dme} = -E_{1/2} + \frac{2.303 RT}{\alpha nF} \log \left\{ \frac{x(5.5-x)}{5(1-x)} \right\} \quad (1)$$

where, $x = i_E/i_{lim}$ (i_E = current at potential E , i_{lim} = limiting current) which is valid in the entire region $0 < x \leq 1$. From the plot of $-E_{dme}$ vs $\log \left\{ \frac{x(5.5-x)}{5(1-x)} \right\}$, the values of $\frac{2.303 RT}{\alpha nF}$ and $E_{1/2}$ were evaluated from the slope and intercept, respectively. Polarographic characteristics are presented in Table 1. For a completely irreversible cathodic

Polarographic Behaviour of Gallium(III) in some Disubstituted Pyridines

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Manuscript received 24 February 1984, revised 21 July 1986, accepted 12 August 1986

THE reduction of gallium(III) at d.m.e. has been studied in presence of some complexing organic reagents by only a few workers¹⁻³. In the present note, we describe the reduction of gallium(III) at d.m.e. in presence of 2,3-dihydroxypyridine (DHP) and 2-amino-3-hydroxypyridine (AHP).

Experimental

Details of the polarograph and the experimental technique have been described in earlier communication⁴. The dropping mercury electrode had the following characteristics: $m^{2/3} t^{1/6} = 2.054 \text{ mg}^{2/3} \text{ s}^{-1/2}$ at zero V (vs S.C.E.) in 0.1 M NaClO₄, $h = 40 \text{ cm}$.

Solutions of DHP and AHP (Aldrich) were prepared in water. Solution of gallium(III) was prepared by dissolving the metallic gallium in perchloric acid. Mixture of perchloric acid and sodium perchlorate (pH 3.0) was used as supporting electrolyte. A 0.01% gelatine was used as the maximum suppressor. Polarograms were recorded for solutions containing $1 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$ Ga^{III} ion and varying amounts of DHP or AHP as the case may be alongwith 0.1 M NaClO₄, HClO₄ (pH 3.0), and maximum suppressor at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$.

Results and Discussion

From the nature of the polarograms and the $E_{1/2}$ values it has been found that reduction of gallium(III) occurred in a single three-electron irreversible and diffusion-controlled step. Half-wave potentials and αn values, where α is the transfer

TABLE 1—POLAROGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS OF Ga^{III} IN PRESENCE AND ABSENCE OF DHP AND AHP LIGANDS

Ga^{III} = $1 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$, $\mu = 0.1 \text{ M NaClO}_4$, pH = 3.0, Temp. = $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$, 0.01% gelatine

System	Ligand mM	$-E_{1/2}$ (V vs S.C.E.)	αn	$\alpha n E_{1/2}$
Ga ^{III} G ^{III} —DHP	0.0	1.289	—	—
	2.0	1.382	0.39	0.036 8
	4.0	1.386	0.38	0.036 8
	6.0	1.390	0.365	0.036 9
	8.0	1.393	0.36	0.037 4
	10.0	1.395	0.36	0.038 1
Ga ^{III} —AHP	2.0	1.377	0.39	0.034 3
	4.0	1.381	0.38	0.034 9
	6.0	1.384	0.37	0.035 1
	8.0	1.387	0.37	0.036 3
	10.0	1.389	0.365	0.036 5

process it may be shown that

$$i/(i_d - i) = 0.886 (t/D)^{1/2} k^0 \frac{\beta_K [L]^K}{\beta_N [L]^N} \quad (2)$$

where, t is the drop time in seconds, D diffusion coefficient in $\text{cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-2}$, β_K and β_N are the stability constants of K and N species and $[L]$ is the concentration of the ligand, k^0 the rate constant in $\text{cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$. If the equilibrium favours the predominance of the highest complex, the equation (2) reduces to

$$\frac{d \log i/(i_d - i)}{d \log [L]} = K - N \quad (3)$$

It was found that the differential of the righthand side in both the cases is the same. Hence, it could be concluded that in both the cases same species suffers reduction at the d.m.e. Complex formation on addition of the ligand was indicated by the change in the half-wave potential, $\Delta E_{1/2}$, ($E_{1/2}$ of Ga^{III} in DHP or AHP - $E_{1/2}$ of Ga^{III} in the supporting electrolyte alone) of the metal ion. The values of $\Delta E_{1/2}$ could be used for comparing the stabilities of complexes found. But in case of irreversible electrode processes, the half-wave potential also depends upon the transfer coefficient, α . A comparison, therefore, could be made only for the values corresponding to the same values of α . Alternatively $\alpha n E_{1/2}$ instead of $E_{1/2}$ could be used⁵.

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It was found that gallium(III)—DHP complex was more stable than gallium(III)—AHP complex. The above finding was in accordance with the class 'a' acceptor nature of Ga^{III} for which it forms stronger bond with an oxygen donor ligand than that with a nitrogen donor ligand. Of the two ligands DHP and AHP, the former could provide ($\bar{O}$, O) bonding and the latter bidentate ($\bar{O}$, N) to Ga^{III}, and hence the stability order DHP > AHP for Ga^{III} complexes.

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**Role of Excess Amount of Secondary Ligand L on Stability of some Heterochelates :
Zinc(II), Cadmium(II) + Iminodiacetic Acid (IMDA) + Biologically Important Amino Acids (L)**

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Manuscript received 9 July 1985, revised 22 August 1986, accepted 5 September 1986

VARIOUS mixed ligand complexes with IMDA as the primary ligand have been studied¹. Bhattacharya *et al.*^{2,3} have investigated the mixed ligand system (MAL) involving bivalent metal ions like Cu^{II}, Ni^{II}, Zn^{II} and histidine, iminodiacetic acid or nitrilotriacetic acid as primary ligand and polyhydroxyphenols or amino acids as secondary ligands.

In the present study, attempt have been made to study the formation constants of the title systems in presence of excess amount of secondary ligand L using modified form of Irving—Rossotti⁴ titration technique.

IMDA is known to form 1 : 1 complex with Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} at pH ~6 and ~6.5, respectively, and is stable at higher pH, where the combination of secondary ligand starts⁵. The reaction can be shown as

$$K_{MAL}^{MA} = \frac{[MAL]}{[MA][L]}$$

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A.R. quality. Metal perchlorates of Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} were prepared from their respective carbonates and their metal content determined. Conductivity water was used in the preparation of all the solutions. The experimental set-up and calculations described by Bhattacharya *et al.* were employed. The measurements were carried out at 30°.

The nature of the potentiometric curves was interpreted as done in earlier publications⁶. In the secondary ligand curve two equivalent extra acid was added in order to account for the extra-hydrogen ions liberated due to the combination of primary ligand IMDA. $\bar{n}$ and pL was calculated using same equation as done earlier⁶. Precise values of K_{MAL}^{MA} were obtained by using the method of averages⁷. The values are presented in Table 1.

Discussion

The order of the formation constants of the ternary complexes in presence of excess amount of secondary ligand L is the same as for the binary complexes^{8,9}. However the values of K_{MAL}^{MA} with excess amount of L significantly lower than K_{ML}^M and K_{MAL}^{ML} of binary complexes but slightly lower than K_{MAL}^{MA} (where M—A—L ratio is 1 : 1 : 1).

TABLE 1—MIXED LIGAND FORMATION CONSTANTS OF SOME HETEROCHELATES OF Zn^{II} AND Cd^{II}

Ionic strength = 0.2 M, Temp. = 30°

Ligand (L)	$\log K_{Zn.L_2}^{Zn^*}$	$\log K_{Zn.L}^{Zn.L}$	$\log K_{Zn.A.L}^{Zn.A}$			$\log K_{Cd.L}^{Cd^*}$	$\log K_{Cd.L_2}^{Cd.L}$	$\log K_{Cd.A.L}^{Cd.A}$		
			(1 : 1 : 1)	(1 : 1 : 1.5)	(1 : 1 : 2.5)			(1 : 1 : 1)	(1 : 1 : 1.5)	(1 : 1 : 2.5)
Glycine	5.22	4.37	4.11	4.07	4.01	4.22	3.69	3.55	3.46	3.40
α -Alanine	5.17	4.10	3.84	3.78	3.70	4.27	3.46	3.40	3.32	3.25
Leucine	4.74	4.36	3.54	3.47	3.41	3.92	3.56	3.00	2.97	2.90
iso-Leucine	4.88	4.33	3.58	3.50	3.42	3.94	3.37	3.00	2.95	2.89
Valine	4.74	4.24	3.50	3.42	3.34	3.91	3.22	3.02	2.98	2.92
Serine	5.06	4.11	4.00	3.93	3.82	3.95	3.80	3.05	3.02	2.95
Threonine	5.16	4.19	4.08	3.98	3.90	4.02	3.20	3.25	3.18	3.05
Methionine	4.69	3.96	3.59	3.49	3.38	4.04	3.15	3.20	3.15	3.02

* Values taken from literature for comparison. $\log K_{MAL}^{MA} = \pm 0.05$ variation.